

Decentralised Identity for Secure Connectivity in Software-defined Networking Environments

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Abstract—Telco operators are using Software Defined Networks (SDN) and Network Function Virtualisation (NFV) to virtualise a wide range of network functions and link or chain them together to create, deploy and deliver network connectivity services. In such a distributed software networking environment, operators use Internet Protocol Security (IPsec) with Internet Key Exchange (IKEv2) to provide secure connectivity between container network functions running on different computing nodes in their infrastructure. This paper discusses the adoption of the Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) model in IKEv2 for authentication purposes to avoid the high costs associated with identity management of IPsec endpoints using Public-Key Infrastructure (PKI) and X.509 certificates, while preserving all the security features of the protocol. The paper presents a novel design of the IKEv2 message flow with Verifiable Credentials (VCs), its open source implementation as a fork of the strongSwan library, and the successful experimental validation.

Index Terms—SDN/NFV, IPsec, IKEv2, SSI, VC

I. INTRODUCTION

Telco operators provide their services leveraging software networks based on the Software Defined Network (SDN) concept [1]. Software-defined networking abstracts the network to enable dynamic network configuration to meet evolving requirements, including quality of service. SDNs decouple control plane and data plane and deploy intelligent controller node(s) in the control plane to (re)-configure on-demand the network infrastructure. On top of such a re-configurable network, operators are also adopting Network Function Virtualisation (NFV) [2] to virtualise a plethora of network functions (*e.g.*, routers, load balancers, firewalls). These functions become LEGO blocks that can be connected or chained together to create, deploy and deliver network connectivity services. Therefore, telecom operators are now running a software network environment to deliver services to their customers for efficiency reasons and, in particular, because the *softwareisation* approach reduces management costs throughout the network and service lifecycle. The need to control management costs is further highlighted by the proliferation of research and development activities around Zero-Touch networks, the next-generation management approach

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that aims to run all heterogeneous operations smoothly and automatically, preferably with 99.9% automation [3].

In such a distributed software network environment, operators typically use Internet Protocol Security (IPsec) [4] to provide secure connectivity between container network functions (or workloads, in Kubernetes jargon) running on different computing nodes of their infrastructure. IPsec [4] consists of a group of network protocols responsible for securing communication between two nodes at the Internet Protocol (IP) layer of the TCP/IP stack. It provides data origin authentication, anti-replay, data integrity and data confidentiality. IPsec is mainly used to set up end-to-end secure tunnels, and it works by encrypting IP packets, along with authenticating the source where they come from. Internet Key Exchange version 2 (IKEv2) [5] is part of the IPsec protocol suite and is responsible for establishing a Security Association (SA) between the IPsec endpoints. An SA is a set of IPsec specifications that are negotiated between the endpoints and includes preferences for the type of authentication and encryption algorithms, keys used, and their lifetime, when establishing the IPsec tunnel. Providing IKEv2 endpoints with secure digital identities is a critical first step in enabling authentication at the heart of SA negotiation. Current solutions rely on a centralised Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) with X.509 certificates [6]. However, this process is largely seen by telco operators as inefficient and costly. The use of PKI and X.509 certificates often requires manual configuration and intervention. For instance, anytime the identity of an endpoint changes or its public key is rotated, the X.509 certificate must be revoked, and a new one must be issued. The revoked certificate must be added to a certificate revocation list, which is not immediately propagated throughout the network. In addition, Certificate Authorities (CAs) come with other drawbacks. They impose a cost on the operator to add a trusted third party into trust relationships (*e.g.*, 5G roaming [7]), and they are vulnerable to a single point of failure, as a single breach can compromise all issued certificates, requiring an update of all endpoint identities before network operations can resume. The use of Subordinate CAs (SubCAs) and high availability mechanisms can reduce the risks but increase the complexity and the cost.

The Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) model [8] represents an alternative solution to overcome the limitations of the

centralized PKI and reduce the complexity and the related cost of X.509 certificate management in large scale networks. SSI is an emerging decentralized digital identity model that gives a node full control over the data it uses to create and prove its identity and the ability to operate autonomously. The composition of the digital identity and the use of a distributed ledger as the Root of Trust (RoT) for public keys reflects the decentralised nature of the SSI model. In fact, the distributed ledger overcomes the single point of failure limitation of the traditional PKI, as no single party is in control of the ledger that contains all public keys. Plus, the separation of public key information, stored in the ledger, from identity attributes, stored in Verifiable Credentials (VCs) [9], also comes with several advantages: (i) a node can rotate its key pair without the need of refreshing the VC, by updating autonomously the information in the ledger, (ii) a node can immediately revoke its Decentralized Identifier (DID) [10] if the key pair gets compromised invalidating right away the VC, (iii) the identity life cycle of a device does not require human intervention, and (iv) the scale at which identity can be provided to nodes increases dramatically.

This paper discusses, for the first time, the adoption of the SSI model in IKEv2 for authentication purposes while preserving all of the protocol's security features. The paper presents a novel design of the IKEv2 message flow with VCs, its open source implementation [11], [12] as a fork of the strongSwan library [13], and its experimental validation. Overall, the paper contributes to simplify network management and reduce the costs associated with identity management for telco operators that use IPsec in their software network environments.

II. BACKGROUND

The architecture of an IPsec node is shown in Fig. 1 and consists of IKEv2 and IPsec engines with the databases for storing Security Associations (SAD) and Security Policies (SPD). The IPsec suite consists of three protocols [14]: Authentication Header (AH), Encapsulating Security Payload (ESP) and IKEv2. The AH and ESP protocols secure IP packets, while IKEv2 protocol [5] is responsible for establishing an SA between the IPsec endpoints to allow ESP or AH packets to flow (*i.e.*, an IPsec tunnel). IKEv2 communication exchanges consist of pairs of messages in the form of a request (from the Initiator) and a response (from the Responder) as shown in Fig. 2.

The first two pairs of messages `IKE_SA_INIT` and `IKE_AUTH` establish the IKE SA. They authenticate both parties and establish encryption keys, and symmetric and integrity-protection algorithms to secure the data exchange. The authentication can occur through digital signature, Message Code Authentication (MAC) with pre-shared key, or Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP) [15].

After `IKE_SA_INIT` and `IKE_AUTH`, a third exchange of messages `CREATE_CHILD_SA` can be used for three purposes: (i) creating the AH or ESP SAs, called IPsec SAs, (ii) re-keying IPsec SAs, and (iii) re-keying IKE SAs. The first

Fig. 1. Architecture of IPsec endpoints.

Fig. 2. IKEv2 message flow, where the suffixes *i* and *r* identify the payloads sent by the Initiator and by the Responder, respectively.

Child SA will be generated directly through the `IKE_AUTH` exchange without invoking the `CREATE_CHILD_SA`.

Each message is made up of a header (HDR) and a set of payloads. Figure 2 shows the IKEv2 flow of messages, detailing the content of the `IKE_SA_INIT` and `IKE_AUTH` messages. In detail, Fig. 2 depicts the case of mutual authentication of parties with certificates.

During the `IKE_SA_INIT` exchange the parties negotiate the cryptographic suite (SA1) that includes an encryption algorithm, an integrity-check algorithm and a pseudo-random function (PRF) for key generation, perform the Diffie-Hellman key exchange (KE) to generate a shared secret, and exchange a nonce (N) for both key generation and protection against the replay attacks. The Responder sends a `CERTREQ` to request a certificate for authentication purposes to the Initiator.

At the end of the first IKEv2 exchange, both parties generate three different symmetric keys: SK_a and SK_e , for integrity protection and encryption of subsequent messages, and SK_d to derive additional key material for Child SAs.

During the `IKE_AUTH` exchange the Initiator asserts its identity (ID), requests a certificate (`CERTREQ`) from the

Fig. 3. Architecture of Centrally Controlled IPsec.

Responder, sends its certificate(s) (CERT), proves its cryptographic identity by signing a block of data with the private key bound to its public key certificate (AUTH, see Section 2.15 of [5] for details), and negotiates the first Child SA (SA2) for secure traffic exchange. Note that the ID is solely used as an internal mechanism to identify SAs and has nothing to do with the one present in the CERT payload.

The Responder replies with the same sequence of payloads. It only skips the CERTREQ payload that was sent previously. It concludes the negotiation of the Child SA with the SA2 payload. Traffic selector (TS) payload allow both parties to identify packets that should be protected according to the Child SA parameters negotiated.

Although IKEv2 provides great flexibility and efficient key agreement, the use of X.509 CERT and associated PKI operations impose high management costs throughout the IKEv2 endpoint identity lifecycle. For this reason, telco operators are exploring alternative architectures to avoid the use of IKEv2. Figure 3 shows the architecture of Centrally Controlled IPsec (CCIPS), which in practice avoid the use of IKE and follows the SDN paradigm for the configuration of IPsec endpoints.

The architecture includes a centralised end-to-end manager, the CCIPS Controller, and two or more agents that operate using an IPsec engine without the need for the IKEv2 protocol. The CCIPS Controller manages the configuration, provisioning, and lifecycle of IPsec channels through the standardised IKE-less data model [16] using well-known telco cloud interfaces (*e.g.*, NETCONF or RESTCONF). The IPsec channel configuration includes agent identification and parameters related to encryption, integrity checks and initialisation vectors relevant to the IPsec protocol. Once configured, the agents populate the SAD and SPD. They locally configure the IPsec engine, run the IPsec stack and establish secure connectivity.

The IKE-less approach offers three benefits, according to telco operators. First, the centralization of security policies (*i.e.*, key lifecycle management, cryptographic algorithms, and key lengths) improves visibility and control while reducing the risk of local misconfiguration. Second, it optimises computational costs by eliminating the need to deploy the IKEv2 protocol and replacing IKEv2 with simplified interfaces. Third, because the CCIPS controller distributes cryptographic keys to

Fig. 4. The Self-Sovereign Identity reference framework.

each endpoint, implicit authentication is achieved inherently (*i.e.*, an IPsec endpoint that is not connected to the controller cannot communicate with other endpoints), eliminating, at least, the need for X.509 certificates for mutual authentication in IKEv2 at the user plane.

This work takes a further step towards efficiency and identity related cost reduction. The proposed decentralised solution retains the great advantage of configuring and establishing IPsec channels with IKEv2, while avoiding the use of X.509 certificates.

III. SELF-SOVEREIGN IDENTITY (SSI)

The SSI reference model [8] consists of three layers depicted in Fig. 4. Each layer contributes to the generation of the digital identity and defines the basic principles for trustworthy interactions between peers in a decentralised manner.

Layer 1 is implemented by means of any Verifiable Data Registry (VDR) that is used to store the public identity data. The Decentralized Identifier (DID) [10] is a new type of globally unique identifier designed to verify a peer. The DID is a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) in the form

`did:method_name:method_specific_id`

where `method-name` is the name of the DID method used to interact with the VDR and `method-specific-id` is the pointer to the DID document stored in the VDR. Thus, a DID associate a peer with a DID document [10] to enable trusted interactions with it. The following is an example of a DID document containing the DID and two verification methods (*i.e.*, public keys) for authentication purpose.

```
"id": "did:method_name:method_specific_id",
"authentication": [{
  "id": "did:method_name:method_spec_id#keys-1",
  "type": "JsonWebKey2020",
  "controller": "did:method_name:method_spec_id",
  "publicKeyJwk": { .. encoded public key .. }
},{
  "id": "did:method_name:method_spec_id#keys-2",
  "type": "JsonWebKey2020",
  "controller": "did:method_name:method_spec_id",
  "publicKeyJwk": { .. encoded public key .. }
}]
```

The DID method [10] is a software implementation used by a peer to interact with the VDR of choice. Following the

W3C recommendation [10], a DID method provides the so-called CRUD functionalities to

- **Create** a DID: generates an identity key pair (sk_{id}, pk_{id}) , the corresponding DID document containing the public key pk_{id} and store the DID document in the VDR at the `method-specific-id` pointed to by the DID,
- **Resolve** a DID: retrieves the DID document from the `method-specific-id` on the VDR pointed to by the DID,
- **Update** a DID: update the content of the DID document, e.g., generates a new key pair (sk'_{id}, pk'_{id}) , and store the modified DID document to the same or a new `method-specific-id` if the peer needs to change the DID, and
- **Deactivate** a DID: provides an evidence in the VDR that the DID has been revoked by the owner.

The DID method implementation is VDR-specific and makes the upper layers independent of the VDR of choice. The DID methods using VDRs implemented by a Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) leverage the immutability features of the DLT that acts as the Root of Trust (RoT) for DID documents, hence public keys.

Layer 2 uses DIDs and DID documents to establish the cryptographic trust between two peers. In principle, both peers prove the ownership of their private key sk_{id} bound to the public key pk_{id} in their DID document.

While Layer 2 uses DIDs to start the authentication, Layer 3 completes it and also deals with authorization to services and/or resources using Verifiable Credentials (VCs) [9]. A VC is an unforgeable digital credential that contains additional characteristics of the digital identity of a peer than its key pair (sk^{id}, pk^{id}) and DID. A VC contains the metadata to describe properties of the credential (e.g., context, id, type, issuer, issuance and expiration dates), most importantly, the DID and the claim(s) about the identity of the peer in the `credentialSubject` field and the information for the verifier of the VC to check the status of revocation of the VC in the `credentialStatus` field. The addition of a proof with the digital signature made the issuer of the VC, makes it tamper-evident and trustworthy.

The combination of identity key pair (sk_{id}, pk_{id}) , DID, and VCs shapes the digital identity of a peer in the SSI ecosystem.

Layer 3 works in accordance with the Triangle-of-Trust where three different roles coexist:

- **Issuer(s)** asserts claims about a peer, creates a VC from these claims, and issues the VC to the Holder. They also manage VC revocation [9] and provide evidences for the Verifiers to check the revocation status [17] of all issued VC without compromising the privacy of the Holders.
- **Holder** owns one or more VCs and generates a Verifiable Presentation (VP) [9] to authenticate with a Verifier and request a service/resource. A VP is constructed as an envelope of the VC issued by an Issuer, where the proof contains the Holder's own signature.
- **Verifier** receives a VP from the Holder and verifies the authenticity by checking the signature made by the Issuer

on the VC and by the Holder on the VP, check the revocation status of the VC and the claim(s) and metadata before granting or rejecting access to the Holder. The Verifier has an implicit trust on the Issuer(s).

On top of these three layers, it is possible to build any ecosystem of trustworthy interactions among peers, taking advantage of a decentralized architecture.

IV. DECENTRALIZED IDENTITY FOR IKEV2 ENDPOINTS

Figure 5 shows for the first time the new IPsec architecture resulting from the integration of SSI into IKEv2. The new IKEv2 design does not require any new payloads, only a slight modification of two existing payloads, `CERTREQ` and `CERT`.

The `CERTREQ` payload is used to request a certificate to the peer. It contains two fields: `Cert Encoding` to express the certificate type, and `Certification Authority` to list the trusted anchors for that type of certificate. The novel design adds a new VC entry to the list of certificate types for the `Cert Encoding` field to support VCs. This is the updated list¹:

Certificate Encoding	Value
PKCS #7 wrapped X.509 certificate	1
PGP Certificate	2
DNS Signed Key	3
X.509 Certificate - Signature	4
Kerberos Token	6
Certificate Revocation List (CRL)	7
Authority Revocation List (ARL)	8
SPKI Certificate	9
X.509 Certificate - Attribute	10
Deprecated (was Raw RSA Key)	11
Hash and URL of X.509 certificate	12
Hash and URL of X.509 bundle	13
OCSF Content	14
Raw Public Key	15
VC	201

When VC is selected as `Cert Encoding`, the `Certification Authority` field must contain the list of DID methods that the sender supports to resolve the peer's DID contained in the VC. A two-byte integer can be considered sufficient to represent all the existing DID methods. The list of currently registered DID methods is maintained by the W3C in [19]. Below is the proposed structure for maintaining the mapping.

```
enum {
    name1 (0),
    name2 (1),
    ...
    (65535)
} DIDMethod
```

In the `Certification Authority` field the first three bytes will indicate the total length of the field, then the next two bytes indicate the length of the list of DID methods and then there is the actual list.

The `CERT` payload carries the party certificate(s) of the type requested in the `CERTREQ` payload. It contains two

¹We assigned the value 201 to the new type `VC`, which is the first value available for private use in the IANA list [18]. Of course, the final value will be defined by IANA once the community has reached a consensus.

Fig. 5. The IPsec architecture with decentralised identity for IKEv2 engines. The IKEv2 engines act as both Holder and Verifier because the IKEv2 endpoints proceed with mutual authentication.

Fig. 6. IKEv2 flow of messages with VC authentication.

fields: `Cert Encoding` to express the selected certificate type and the `Certificate Data` that carries the content of the certificate. The list of possible values for the `Cert Encoding` is the same we propose for the `CERTREQ` payload. When VC type is selected, the `Certificate Data` field contains the content of the VC. To improve the data transfer efficiency, it is possible to use the Concise Binary Object Representation (CBOR) format [20].

Figure 6 shows the IKEv2 flow of messages in the case of mutual authentication with VCs. The Responder sends the `CERTREQ` payload with the VC certificate type and the list of DID methods it supports. During the authentication phase, the initiator checks the availability of the VC for authentication. It then checks that the DID in the VC matches one of the DID methods previously sent by the Responder. If either of these conditions is not met, the Initiator ignores the `CERTREQ` payload and will not send the `CERT` payload without causing an error condition of the IKEv2 protocol, similar to what happens with other certificate types when there is no match. If both of these conditions are met, the Initiator sends the `CERT` payload containing the VC, and the `AUTH` payload with the signature for identity proof over the same content of the original IKEv2 protocol, as discussed in Section II. Note that the Initiator signs using the private key (sk) associated with the public key (pk) stored in the DID document to which its DID points.

Upon receiving the `IKE_AUTH Request`, the Responder checks (i) the VC against schema specified in the `@context` field, (ii) the validity of the metadata and the revocation status of the VC, (iii) resolves the DID of the Issuer and verifies its signature on the VC, (iv) extracts the Initiator's DID from the `credentialSubject` field of the VC and resolves it to the Initiator DID document to retrieve the public key and, finally, (v) verifies the signature in the `AUTH` payload. If all checks are successful, the Responder authenticates the Initiator and proceeds with other IKEv2 operations. The Responder authenticates itself to the Initiator in the same way.

In accordance with the SSI working principles described in Section III, a Holder wraps the VC, together with a nonce from the Verifier, in a VP and signs it before presenting it to a Verifier for authentication. In IKEv2, the generation of the signature in the `AUTH` payload does not include the `CERT` payload, which carries the VC. However, the data block signed by both the Responder and the Initiator contains the nonce sent by the other party. This nonce binds the VC to the specific session, replicating the challenge-response mechanism with VPs.

V. SECURITY CONSIDERATIONS

All security considerations addressed in [5] hold. The design here presented does not change any pre-existing operating principle of the IKEv2 protocol. However, some considerations about the DID resolution process are worth discussing. Assuming that a DID resolution is performed in clear, a man in the middle could impersonate the VDR node, forge a DID document containing the authenticating endpoint's DID, associate it with a key pair that he owns, and then return it to the DID resolver. Thus, the attacker could reuse a VC while being able to compute a valid signature in the `AUTH` payload and be authenticated. A reasonable solution to this attack could be to create an IPsec tunnel with the VDR node hosted and operated by the telco operator using `Raw Public Key` for authentication.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

The new design has been implemented in `strongSwan` [13], a world reference open source library, written in C, that supports the entire IPsec framework. The novel open source implementation [11], [12] involves slight modifications to

Fig. 7. The high-level architecture of the overall solution.

TABLE I
EXPERIMENTAL LATENCY RESULTS OF THE IKEV2 PROTOCOL WITH X.509 AND VC CERTIFICATE TYPES [MS]

CERT Type	Total	Δ	Initiator Construct CERT	Responder Construct CERT	Initiator Construct AUTH	Responder Construct AUTH	Initiator Process Peer CERT	Responder Process Peer CERT	Initiator Process Peer AUTH	Responder Process Peer AUTH
X.509	36,744	21,393	0,329	0,294	4,083	1,705	0,489	0,535	4,857	3,059
VC	72,634	19,175	0,222	0,143	3,778	3,506	18,910	21,088	2,319	3,494

two sub-libraries, *libstrongswan* that contains basic functions employed by the other components and *libcharon* that implements the IKEv2 protocol. The *libcharon* library has been extended to support the construction and processing of CERT and AUTH payloads with VCs. The *libstrongswan* library has been extended with two brand new credential interfaces: *verifiable_credential* and *decentralized_identifier*.

In line with the strongSwan development approach, the two novel interfaces have been implemented through a novel loadable plugin called *vc_iota*, as depicted in Fig.7. The current implementation leverages the previously developed *identity-cbindings* [12] library, thus offloading VC and DID handling to the IOTA Identity framework [21].

The *vc_iota* plugin has two components: *vc_iota* that implements the *verifiable_credential* interface and *did_iota* that implements the *decentralized_identifier* interface.

The main functions in *did_iota* are:

- *did_iota_gen*: generates the endpoint's identity key pair (*sk*, *pk*) and the DID document;
- *did_iota_load*: loads the endpoint's DID document and *sk* into memory;
- *did_iota_sign*: signs the AUTH message with *sk*;
- *did_get_encoding*: returns the DID document either in PEM or DER format.

The main functions in *vc_iota* are:

- *vc_iota_gen*: generates the endpoint's VC;
- *vc_iota_load*: loads the endpoint's VC into memory before IKEv2 protocol starts, or when the endpoint receives the peer's VC during IKEv2 protocol it verifies the authenticity of the VC and then loads it into memory;
- *vc_iota_verify*: verifies the peer's AUTH message with the proper *pk* retrieved from the VDR;
- *vc_get_encoding*: returns the VC either in PEM or DER format.

The IKEv2 endpoints first create their self-sovereign identity with the *pki --gen* command for testing purposes in strongSwan. The command now includes the *iota* option to allow the endpoint to generate his DID, DID document, and VC through the *vc_iota* plugin. The application first calls the *did_iota_gen* function to generate the key pair (*sk*, *pk*) and the DID document, and then the *vc_iota_gen* function to generate the VC. Finally, it stores the VC and the DID document (plus the *sk*) in two different PEM files by invoking the respective *get_encoding* functions.

Both the Initiator and Responder start the *charon* daemon to run the IKEv2 protocol. They then load into the daemon their configuration and credentials using the *swanctl --load-all* command. The application loads the endpoint's DID Document (plus the *sk*) and the VC into memory by calling the *did_iota_load* and *vc_iota_load* functions. Both peers call the *vc_get_encoding* function to return the VC in DER format and embed it in the CERT payload during the authentication phase of the IKEv2 protocol. They then signs the AUTH payload using the *did_iota_sign* function. Both peers process the CERT and AUTH payloads by calling the *vc_iota_load* function to validate and store the received VC in the IOTA Identity structures, and the *vc_iota_verify* function to verify the received signature.

VII. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

To validate the design and assess the performance of the new decentralised VC-based authentication during key exchange, the new strongSwan was deployed on two off-the-shelf desktops equipped with a quad-core CPU clocked at 1.8 GHz, 4 GB of RAM, a Gigabit Ethernet interface. The desktops are connected via a layer 2 switch, and both have access to a DLT node to resolve the peer's DID. The desktops leverage the immutability feature of the public IOTA Tangle and interact with it through an IOTA node operated in the lab.

The IKEv2 endpoints resolve the peer DID with an HTTP request served by the IOTA node. Initiator and Responder use EdDSA for the three-link X.509 certificate chains and VCs. A total of 1000 runs were performed for each configuration to collect statistically relevant results on key exchange latency.

Table I shows the average latency of the key exchange from the *IKE_SA_INIT* Request to the end of the processing the *IKE_AUTH* Response on the Initiator side. The column Δ shows the time share spent on all operations not related to authentication, and since the tests of both authentication options were carried out under the same conditions, the averages are almost equal. The following columns show the latencies of the different authentication related steps such as CERT and AUTH payload construction and processing. The sum of all these columns is equal to the total key exchange latency. The latency components are in the same order of magnitude, with the exception of the CERT payload processing. With VC type of certificate the IKEv2 endpoint must resolve the DIDs of the Issuer and the peer in order to retrieve (i) the public keys for signature verification on the VC (of the Issuer) and then on the AUTH payload (of the Holder, *i.e.*, the peer), and (ii) the revocation status of the VC. The need for DID resolutions increases the total key exchange latency when using the VC

certificate type. However, the overall IKEv2 latency remains in the millisecond range, so the increase is negligible in practice given the slow dynamics of the IPsec tunnel configuration in today's software telco network environments, which typically range from minutes to hours.

It is worth noting that the increased latency is offset by the huge benefit of reduced identity management costs. In fact, an IKEv2 endpoint generates its own identity in a self-sovereign manner and only re-contacts the Issuer for renewal when its VC expires. During the validity period of a VC, the IKEv2 endpoint can rotate its key pair without requesting a new VC by autonomously updating the DID document in the ledger; on the other hand, a new X.509 certificate is required each time a new key pair is generated, along with the entire certificate lifecycle management. Moreover, processing of the CERT payload with the VC certificate type includes a free VC revocation status check; today telco operators either perform a costly Certificate Revocation List (CRL) management process or, more often, skip X.509 revocation management with obvious security risks. Furthermore, an IKEv2 endpoint can immediately and autonomously revoke its DID if the key pair gets compromised invalidating right away the VC; in the case of using X.509 certificates, the compromise triggers a lengthy process consisting of a revocation request to the CA and subsequent CRL update and dissemination. Overall, the self-sovereign identity lifecycle of an IKEv2 endpoint requires minimal human intervention in line with the Zero-Touch paradigm, and the scale at which identity can be provided to endpoints increases dramatically.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper discusses, for the first time, the adoption of the SSI model in IKEv2 for authentication purposes to avoid the high costs associated with identity management of IPsec endpoints using PKI with X.509 certificates. The novel IKEv2 message flow with VCs preserves all of the protocol's security features, and experimental evaluation of the open source implementation as a fork of the strongSwan library shows efficient results. The resulting solution is viable in real-world deployments, thus simplifying network management and reducing identity management costs for telco operators that use IPsec in their software networking environments.

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